

Prepositional phrases as postmodification patterns of the noun phrase in learner
English writing across cohorts

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This is a learner corpus study in progress, and it analyses the grammatical complexity of the noun phrase, based on Biber, et al's hypothesised developmental index (2011). This presentation focuses on features of postmodification, namely prepositional phrases starting with 'of' and 'other prepositions' as described by the framework, and how these features are associated with the learners' cohorts (year 3, 4, 5 undergraduate programme) in academic writing as a foreign language. Dataset were taken from the CELTEC, a 246,808-word learner corpus compiled with the writings of future teachers of English in Chile for the purpose of this study. Preliminary results indicate that prepositional phrases starting with other prepositions than 'of' is the single most common modification pattern in this corpus across the three cohorts with a frequency of occurrence of 56.3 normalised to a thousand words. Besides, a slow increase in the frequency of occurrence can be observed in the three cohorts: year 3 has a frequency of 54, year 4 of 56, and year 5 a frequency of 60.5 prepositional phrases per one thousand words. Additionally, prepositional phrases starting with 'of' has an overall frequency of occurrence of 19.3 which makes it the fourth most frequent modification pattern in CELTEC. Similarly, prepositional phrases starting with 'of' show a moderate but steady increment in the frequency of occurrence across cohorts: year 3 with 16.6; year 4 with 19.1; and finally, year 5 a frequency of 23 prepositional phrases per one thousand words. Preliminary, postmodification in the noun phrase by means of prepositional phrases seems to increase both in frequency and length across cohorts.